

Thesis Word Counting

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This document outlines the procedure used to count words in my physics PhD thesis to be submitted to the University of Warwick. Word counting was complicated by my thesis including my papers.

Procedure:

1) Main Text

Main text is counted using Overleaf's Word Count feature. Figures, tables, algorithms, references, and appendices are turned into comments beforehand so that they could be counted separately.

2) Figures

Figures are uncommented and the resulting change in document length is recorded. How to include illustrations in a word count is not specified by university regulations. However, the Department of Physics suggests estimating a word count based on image area. An average density of 350 words/page is nominated; however, I use a nominal density of 400 to be safe. I think it's better to estimate a word count that's a bit too high than a word count that's a bit too low.

Including papers is complicated as, nominally, they may be typeset with different margins than my thesis. However, most figures are larger than necessary, so I do not think that corresponding differences in figure size are an issue. Another potential issue is that it is not clear how to include figure captions, so I count captions as part of the image area. Caption word density is higher than the nominal figure word density; however, I assume that increased density is compensated for by extra whitespace above and below captions.

3) Tables

Tables and their captions are not included in the word count. Many of my figures are sheets of example images, which could be described as tables and therefore not count according to university regulations. However, I include all my figures in my word count to ensure that I do not underestimate.

4) Algorithms

These are copied into Microsoft Word with their captions for word counts.

5) Appendices

Appendices usually have a separate length limit to the main thesis content. However, permission is granted by the Chair of the Board of Graduate Studies for such length limits to not apply to my thesis in the understanding that my appendices are not usually crucial to the understanding or examination of my thesis.

6) Bibliography

Content such as references, title page, research training, acknowledgements, declarations, data availability statements, conflict of interest statements, and any other bibliographic content is not included in the word count.

Ambiguity

There is no recommended tool for thesis word counting, and what counts is sometimes vague or unspecified. How exactly do we count variables in equations? What about abbreviations – do we count the abbreviation once or for each abbreviated word? How do we count illustrations and, further, how do we count tabulated illustrations? Do we count algorithms?

Overall, there is a lot of uncertainty. Thus, I think that best practice is to use common sense. I suspect that a difficult examiner or administrator could argue thesis length by +/- 5%. To be safe, I have therefore ensured that my thesis is at least 10% shorter than the word limit.